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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13337625>

PECULIARITIES OF PREPARING A TEACHER TO WORK IN AN INCLUSIVE EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT AT THE PRESENT STAGE OF HIGHER EDUCATION DEVELOPMENT

Abstract.

The authors emphasise the importance of training teachers to work in an inclusive educational environment in the context of current social requirements, modernisation of national legislation, international educational narratives of humanity pedagogy and the activities of modern Ukrainian teachers in the limited conditions of war. The peculiarities of such training include the need to modernise its organisational and pedagogical conditions.

Keywords. *Inclusive educational environment, teacher training, teacher's readiness for inclusion, higher education.*

Currently, inclusion is considered a strategic task in the development of educational systems in many countries, including Ukraine. This is driven by several prerequisites, such as legislative and normative frameworks, societal demands, theoretical perspectives, and practical orientations. In particular, the social prerequisites that create the need to include children with special educational needs (hereinafter referred to as SEN) in the environment of normally developing peers include: shifting educational goals from knowledge-based to competency-based, humanizing society and education, implementing the principle of equal opportunities in education for all children, transitioning from a "medical" to a "social" model of disability, involving parents as active participants in the educational process, and embracing international inclusive practices.

According to foreign researchers (M. Ainscow, T. Booth, B. Cagran, A. De Boer, J.-R. Kim, A. Minnaert, S. J. Pijl, M. Schmidt, K. Scorgie, and others), a fundamental and crucial condition for the development of an inclusive educational environment is the preparation of competent teachers capable of and willing to work effectively with children with special educational needs.

The issue of improving the quality of training for future specialists in inclusion to perform various professional functions has been addressed by numerous researchers, including V. Bondar, G. Davidenko, S. Myronova, N. Pakhomova, K. Ostrovska, P. Talanchuk, V. Tyshchenko, M. Chaykovsky, A. Shevtsov, D. Shulzhenko, and others.

In recent years, interest in the problem of training such teachers in higher education institutions, both through formal, non-formal and informal education, has increased significantly.

The shortage of personnel in this field and the limited professional resources due to the war necessitate a revision of approaches to professional training in the field of inclusion.

Higher education is acquiring a greater social content, as the university mission now includes such a

component as the labor market, indicating interactions between employers and educational institutions, expanding the range of social professions, and regulating the relationship between the individual and social institutions. The rapid development of scientific and technological progress drives the implementation of pedagogical innovations, modernization of forms, and technologization of educational processes in the training of teachers in higher education institutions [8, p.391].

Global experience shows that the organization of inclusive education increases the demands on teachers' activities and expands their functional responsibilities. Moreover, professional and personal characteristics undergo changes. In such conditions, a teacher cannot limit himself or herself to knowledge of the specifics of general education subjects, general education programmes and traditional teaching methods. Relying solely on existing pedagogical skills and abilities proves insufficient. The active development of inclusive practices requires new didactic models and different organization of professional teacher training [1, c. 78].

In the process of such training, teachers undergo changes at both the personal and activity levels. At the personal level, individual and moral-psychological qualities are formed, defining attitudes towards professional activities. At the activity level, in addition to the accumulation of knowledge, students form a system of motives, attitudes, attitudes that provide an opportunity to effectively perform professional functions [3, c. 207].

The modern preparation of teachers for work in inclusive educational environments requires modernization of its organizational and pedagogical conditions, achieved by:

- ensuring close ties with modern scientific research and academic research institutions/laboratories to introduce the latest pedagogical technologies;
- combining in-depth study of core subjects with specific (elective) courses to foster innovative thinking;

- support for applicants in exploring current issues of inclusive education and creating conditions to provide an innovative foundation for scientific research;
- effectively engaging stakeholders of educational programs and maximizing their involvement in the educational process of higher education institutions.

Some scholars consider the essence of training as a process of transformation of teachers' professional activity, the result of which should be the formation of a subjective position on the basis of which conclusions about the nature of readiness can be drawn. They identify criteria that can be used to determine a teacher's readiness to proactively improve their professional activity and themselves in terms of inclusion.

The first criterion identified by the researchers is motivational and value-based, manifested in the desire to transform personal experience, construct professional activities, self-education and cooperation.

The next (operational-activity) criterion includes mastery of professional knowledge development methods (internalization) and updating professional abilities (externalisation), as well as improving activities (correction of externalisation). And the last (Reflective-evaluative) criterion is the ability to formulate difficulties and problems of professional life, interpret their causes, and evaluate the results of professional and personal achievements of the teacher.

Each of the above theoretical approaches to teacher training undoubtedly contains a rational grain, requiring consideration in the work with adult learners during in-service training courses. The criteria proposed by the authors are of great interest for our study, as they reflect the entire structure of readiness, including its personal, value, knowledge, activity and reflection components [4, c. 182].

An equally important feature of the readiness of an inclusion specialist is the strengthening of the axiological aspect of teacher training, which provides a professional and humanistic orientation and ensures the formation of professional values aimed at achieving humanistic goals and implementing humanistic principles regarding children with special educational needs.

The preparation process should develop the components of a teacher's professional competence, namely:

- professional pedagogical positions, teacher's attitudes, necessary for his/her profession (value-semantic component);
- professional (objectively necessary) pedagogical knowledge (cognitive component);
- professional (objectively necessary) pedagogical skills (activity component);
- personal qualities that enable teachers to master professional knowledge and skills (personal component).

During teacher preparation, their professional competence structure should form three substructures: activity, communicative, and personal. These substructures ensure teachers possess pedagogical knowledge, means for pedagogical actions, various methods of pedagogical communication, and reflect pedagogical tact, reflection, orientation, thinking, and goal-setting [2, c. 102].

To describe the process of preparing teachers for their new field of inclusive activity, many researchers reveal the qualitative characteristics of both the training itself and the teacher in particular.

For example, foreign researcher J. Corbett suggests four components of an inclusive culture that need to be developed in teachers:

- respectful attitudes towards perspectives absent in their personal life experience;
- teachers' awareness of the fact that intellectually developed people are found not only among those with high social and academic status;
- Recognition of equal educational and social development rights for all learners and addressing these rights considering each child's individual needs;
- conscious adherence to true pedagogical priorities and values.

The content of preparing teachers for inclusive education can only be determined by considering trends in the development of inclusion in both national and international theory and practice. This approach will help to avoid mistakes and select an appropriate strategy for the professional development of teachers providing educational services to students with special educational needs. [5, p. 214].

The process of qualitative interaction between the subjects of the educational space can be possible only based on updating the complex of professional knowledge, skills, personal life experience, value orientation, professional and personal qualities, encapsulated in the concept of "professional competence". In characterizing this concept, the key elements are not just knowledge, skills, and abilities but their actualization ability for solving cognitive or practical life tasks [7, p. 129].

The content part of the teacher training system involves comprehensive, in-depth psycho-pedagogical study of each child's characteristics, enabling individualized corrective influence methods in case of developmental deviations. Both domestic and international research data indicate a steady increase in such children. Consequently, the issues of quality preparation of educators-organizers for the correctional-pedagogical process are quite relevant today.

As a subject of special education, the correctional teacher's professional characteristics determine the success of curriculum implementation, the quality of educational services, and the upbringing and education of students with special educational needs. Children must not only acquire knowledge but also master specific technologies and adapt to society. For a child to become a full-fledged subject of life, the teacher must first become such a subject [6].

Thus, at the current stage of educational development towards expanding inclusive educational environments, specially trained specialists are needed. Therefore, it is very important to prepare teachers for their work, provide them with tools and models of innovative teaching, and help them to master in-depth knowledge of their subject, technologies, and methods of working with children with special educational needs.

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